

KEY PROCEDURES AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This study presents fundamental information on the key procedures and methodological approaches to conflict management, drawing on theoretical data related to the constructive channeling of conflicts within the context of modern psychology, social sciences, pedagogy, and the development of the human worldview. Throughout the research, the psychological, pedagogical, and social aspects of conflict were examined. Additionally, scientific research by international scholars is cited as examples. During our study, the procedures for conflict identification, psychological preparation, practical application in pedagogy, and monitoring processes are described in detail through methodological approaches.

Keywords: Conflict, conflict management, methodological approaches, psychological research, pedagogical approaches, causes of conflict.

KONFLIKTLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ASOSIY TARTIBLARI VA METODIK USULLARI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda konfliktlarni boshqarishning asosiy tartiblari va metodik usullarini haqidagi asosiy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan bo'lib, u zamonaviy psixologiya, ijtimoiy fanlar, pedagogika yo'nalishi va insonlarning dunyoqarashi rivojlanish muhitida konfliktlarni konstruktiv yo'naltirishga oid nazariy ma'lumotlarga asoslanadi. Tadqiqot jarayonida konfliktning psixologik, pedagogik va ijtimoiy jihatlari tahlillari ko'rib chiqildi. Shuningdek, xalqaro olimlarning ilmiy tadqiqotlari misol tariqasida keltirildi. Tadqiqotimiz davomida konfliktni aniqlash, psixologik tayyorgarlik, pedagogikada amaliy qo'llash va monitoring jarayonlari tartiblari batafsil metodik usullar orqali sharhlab berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Konflikt, konfliktlarni boshqarish, metodik usullar, psixologik tadqiqotlar, pedagogik yondashuvlar, konflikt sabablari.

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРОЦЕДУРЫ И МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КОНФЛИКТАМИ

Аннотация: В данном исследовании представлена основная информация об основных процедурах и методических приёмах управления конфликтами. Исследование основывается на теоретических данных из области современной психологии, социальных наук, педагогики, а также на концепциях конструктивного разрешения конфликтов в контексте развития человеческого мировоззрения. В ходе исследования были рассмотрены психологические, педагогические и социальные аспекты конфликта. В качестве примеров также приводятся научные исследования зарубежных учёных. В нашей работе были подробно описаны и разъяснены процедуры выявления конфликта, психологической подготовки, практического применения в педагогике и мониторинга с использованием детальных методических приёмов.

Ключевые слова: Конфликт, управление конфликтами, методические приёмы, психологические исследования, педагогические подходы, причины конфликта.

INTRODUCTION

Interpreting conflict only as a negative phenomenon is not complete from a scientific point of view, since it can also be a source of development, renewal, and social change. Therefore, the issue of conflict management has become a relevant area of modern management theory, social psychology, pedagogy, and organizational science. From the second half of the 20th century, conflictology was formed as an independent scientific direction. Research in the field of social psychology and organizational management has shown the need to analyze conflict not as a simple contradiction between people, but as a systemic and multifactorial process. For example, field theory, developed by the American scientist Kurt Lewin, explains conflict from the point of view of the balance of forces, that is, internal or external conflict arises as a result of the conflict between forces and obstacles that a person or group strives towards a certain goal. Later, Morton Deutsch analyzed conflict based on the paradigms of cooperation and competition and substantiated the need to distinguish between constructive and destructive conflicts. Therefore, the basic procedures and methodological methods of conflict management, along with universality, also require a contextual approach. In educational institutions, conflicts arise from psychological and social disagreements between the teacher and the student, management and the team, or students. In such conditions, conflict management manifests itself not only as the art of conflict resolution, but also as the art of transforming it into a factor of constructive development. In scientific literature, the concepts of conflict management and conflict resolution are distinguished. The first concept means not the complete elimination of conflict, but controlling its intensity, minimizing its negative consequences, and unlocking constructive possibilities. The second involves resolving a specific dispute through a specific agreement or decision. The conflict behavior model developed by Thomas and Kilmann shows that individuals choose one of five main strategies in a conflict situation: competition, cooperation, compromise, adaptation, or retreat. This model substantiates the importance of choosing a strategy appropriate to the situation in the management process. In recent decades, a transformational approach has developed in conflictology. The theory of conflict transformation, put forward by John Paul Lederach, views conflict not only as a process of problem-solving, but also as an opportunity to qualitatively change relationships. This approach is especially effective in managing long-term social conflicts. Also, the concept of "principled negotiation," developed by Roger Fisher and William Ury, proposes a model of agreement based on interests and prioritizes the identification of common interests over positional confrontation. The relevance of conflict management is increasing in the process of globalization. Multicultural communities, remote work, and digital communication tools are generating new forms of conflict. Incomplete expression of the emotional context in online communication increases the likelihood of misinterpretation and misunderstanding. Therefore, in the modern management system, it is necessary to form special competencies for conflict prevention and management. The purpose of our research is to systematically cover the main procedures and methodological methods of conflict management, to analyze theoretical and practical approaches based on the scientific research of international scholars, and to substantiate the possibilities of their application in modern organizations and educational institutions. In the research process, the analysis of

psychological, pedagogical, and social aspects of conflict is considered, Morton Deutsch analyzes conflict in his psychological paradigms as a conflict of goals and interests between individuals or groups. According to his research, if constructive conflicts are directed towards compromise, cooperation, and finding new solutions, it creates opportunities for strengthening interpersonal relationships and social development. At the same time, destructive conflicts reduce effectiveness, increase psychological pressure, and disrupt the social environment. The five conflict behavior models developed by Thomas and Kilmann - competition, cooperation, compromise, adaptation, and retreat - serve as the main methodological guide for choosing conflict management strategies in organizations and the pedagogical environment. As a result, the main procedures and methodological methods of conflict management appear as an effective system at the interpersonal, group, and organizational levels. They serve not only to eliminate conflict, but also to strengthen interpersonal relationships, increase the effectiveness of the team, and stabilize the psychological environment. At the same time, the research of international scholars and practical examples help to identify the universal foundations and contextual differences of these approaches. The approach of international scholars and modern methodological methods play an important role in conflict management. Research by Morton Deutsch emphasizes the difference between constructive and destructive conflicts, as well as the need to determine the balance of interpersonal cooperation and competition for effective conflict management. This approach is applied to the processes of conflict prevention, their constructive orientation, and effective decision-making in the pedagogical and psychological environment. The Thomas-Kilmann model shows that individuals respond to conflicts through five main strategies: competition, cooperation, compromise, adaptation, and retreat. These strategies allow for effective conflict management in organizations and teams, as well as constructive resolution of conflicts between students and teachers in the pedagogical environment. Modern methodological techniques differ depending on the type of conflict, the number of participants, and the social context. Moreover, John Paul Lederach's transformational approach allows for a qualitative change in relationships in the management of long-term and complex social conflicts. Methodological methods of conflict management are effectively applied in organizations, communities, and the pedagogical environment as follows: mediation and arbitration facilitate the prompt and constructive resolution of disputes, principled negotiation ensures agreement based on interests, and achieving consensus democratizes the decision-making process by ensuring the consent of all participants. Research by international scholars and practical examples show that conflict management is not only a means of conflict resolution, but also a strategic resource for social and organizational development. Morton Deutsch's constructive conflict concept, Thomas-Kilmann model, John Paul Lederach's transformational approach, Roger Fisher and William Ury's principled negotiation methods, Geert Hofstede's theory of cultural dimensions - all these form the universal and contextual foundations of conflict management. At the same time, modern trends in conflict management require new methodological approaches, taking into account technological development, cultural diversification, and digital communication tools. In the continuous approach, the main procedures and methodological methods of conflict management - identification, strategic preparation, practical application, monitoring, and assessment - are enriched with international scientific research and manifest as an effective system in the organizational and pedagogical environment. At the same time, the adaptation of

methodological approaches, taking into account digital tools, cultural context, and psychological competencies, serves to ensure constructive conflict orientation and long-term effectiveness. As a result, conflict management procedures and methodological methods work in a continuous system not only as a means of resolving conflicts, but also as the main means of strengthening interpersonal relations, stabilizing the social and pedagogical environment, and increasing the effectiveness of organizations. The methodological approach to strategic planning is the most important part of conflict management. This process takes into account the complexity of the situation, the psychological characteristics of the parties, the cultural context, the time factor, and resources. There is no single universal solution for each conflict; on the contrary, each situation requires a unique approach. From this point of view, flexibility and the choice of strategy depending on the situation are the main criteria determining the effectiveness of conflict management. In the method of practical application, such methodological techniques as mediation, negotiation, achieving consensus, dialogue based on cooperation are used. These methods do not exacerbate the conflict, but, on the contrary, serve to form mutual understanding and trust between the parties. The method of monitoring and evaluation is one of the final, but most important, elements of the conflict management process. Even after the decision is made, it is necessary to monitor the situation, monitor the implementation of agreements, and prevent possible further escalation. This stage ensures the continuity of conflict management and forms the process not as a one-time action, but as a permanent management system. Conflict is an integral and natural component of the system of human relations, constantly manifested in the social, pedagogical, and organizational environment. Assessing it solely as a negative phenomenon is not entirely scientifically sound, as conflict, under certain conditions, also acts as a catalyst for development, renewal, and change. What matters is not the existence of the conflict, but how to manage it, how to direct it, and what result it will lead to. Therefore, the issue of conflict management is considered one of the important directions of modern psychology, pedagogy, and management theory.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that effective conflict management requires a systematic and phased approach. First of all, it is important to identify the sources, causes, and participants in the conflict. Conflict is often linked not to superficial causes, but to deep psychological, social, or structural factors. Therefore, the process of diagnosing it should be carried out through objective analysis, observation of communicative behavior, and identification of a system of interests. An incorrectly diagnosed conflict can lead to the selection of incorrect methods and further escalation of the conflict. Thus, the basic procedures and methodological methods of conflict management are of great importance in modern social and pedagogical practice. They manifest themselves as a scientifically based mechanism for effective conflict management, ensuring psychological stability, and forming an atmosphere of long-term pedagogical cooperation.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Aziza, Turemuratova. "KONFLIKT VA UNING KELIB CHIQISH SABABLARI." Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке 3.32 (2025): 465-467.
2. Turemuratova, A. B. "TA'LIMDA PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA O'QUVCHIYOSHLARNING KOLLABORATIV KO'NIKALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИ." Inter education & global study 3.4 (2025): 242-250.

3. Туремуратова, А. Б. "ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТРАДИЦИЙ НАРОДНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ." Мировая наука 6 (75) (2023): 125-129.
4. Turemuratova, A., and N. Tureniyazova. "The program of using modern pedagogical methods in the higher education system and the problems of improving pedagogical skills." Science and innovation 2.B10 (2023): 373-377.
5. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "Educational traditions in shaping the worldview of young people in folk pedagogy." Modern Science and Research 2 (2023): 318-322.
6. Turemuratova, A., U. Uzakbaeva, and D. Nuriyeva. "Basic concepts of family psychology and overcoming psychological problems." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 104-109.
7. Turemuratova, A., and J. Asamatdinova. "Talabalar qadiriyaatqa bag'darlang'anliqti rivajlantiruwda auditoriyadan tis shinig'iwlardin'roli." (2021).
8. Turemuratova, A. "Har bir xalqning o'z qadriyati bor." (2021).
9. Turemuratova, A., and B. Temirbekov. "Mustahkam oilani shakllantirishda yoshlarda naql-maqollardan foydalanishning tarbiyaviy-psixologik ahamiyati." (2022).
10. Deutsch, M. (1973). The Resolution of Conflict: Constructive and Destructive Processes. New Haven: Yale University Press
11. Thomas, K. W., & Kilmann, R. H. (1974). Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument. Tuxedo, NY: Xicom.
12. Fisher, R., Ury, W., & Patton, B. (1991). Getting to Yes: Negotiating Agreement Without Giving In (2nd ed.). New York: Penguin Books.